

ACINO

Application-Centric IP/optical
Network Orchestration

ACINO/D3.3

Cross layer planning and optimization strategies

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Summary

This document highlights the defined strategies for the cross-layer planning procedures which will in turn define the algorithmic functions and approaches for the development of the multi-layer optimization module, the online planning tool module and their interfaces with the rest of the modules in the ACINO orchestrator. The terms “cross-layer” and “multi-layer” are used interchangeably with the same meaning; the former conforms to the original task name, while the latter is more prevalent in the existing literature.

We first define the problem and present the existing work in the field. Then we show the flow of information in the ACINO architecture pertaining to multi-layer optimization. Following this the strategies for the implementation of the multi-layer processes and modules are described in detailed. The simulation environment and some preliminary results are shown at the end of the document.

1 Definition of the application centric multi-layer planning problem

Planning problems have been widely described for various types of networks. This introductory section defines first the terminology for the multi-layer planning problem, and then extends it into an application centric approach, which is the aim of the ACINO project.

1.1 Planning problem definition

In a general way, the goal of the planning techniques is to help the network operator to obtain a better network utilization with subsequent performance improvement. Figure 1.1 illustrates a schema with the main blocks in a planning problem. These include five blocks:

- **Service/Traffic demands.** These are the information that customers need the network transport. There are many features that determine a given traffic demand. A fixed matrix with end-to-end peak rates can be the input to the problem, but more complicated processes may be defined, for instance, with random or time-dependent traffic variations. Moreover, the traffic demands can be split by services and each service can have different requirements.
- **Network Equipment.** It is composed by the hardware that is deployed in the network, including routers, ROADMs and the cables or fibres that connect them and their software. Operators invest on infrastructure and planning tools help to improve the network capacity task, but once the equipment is deployed in the network, planning process must deal with the available resources and not just the optimal configuration.
- **Objective.** This is a critical aspect of every engineering problem. It is very important to properly define what aspects the planning problem must either solve or improve. Congestion avoidance can be the target of a planning process, but also it can be the minimization of the investment. This depends on the operator's requirements and the offered capabilities by the network infrastructure.

Figure 1.1: Planning problem flow chart

- **Planning module.** This module must be able to get the traffic information and network equipment, and provide the optimum network configuration solution according to the operator's requirements set by the specific objectives.
- **Network configuration.** This is the solution to the previous problem and it is translated in a change of the network equipment configuration. The solution can also suggest more equipment to be deployed in the network.

1.2 Extension to multi-layer problems

The previous definition is a general way to explain how a planning process is carried out and which are the different elements that must be considered. However, practically the information flows in the network over multiple technology layers. In general, these layers include: a) the IP layer (or practically the extended IP/MPLS layer) for the routing of the common data oriented services, b) the WDM layer for the high capacity transport of the aggregated traffic over the network links and c) the OTN (Optical Transport Network) layer which offers the advanced opto-electronic grooming and switching capabilities to the optical layer. These layers can be controlled and optimised independently, thus also the planning process can be implemented without considering the other layers. This is actually true (and rather practical) when the WDM layer (with or without OTN support) is considered purely as data transport layer, which provides only end-to-end static connections serving the overlay IP demands.

However, as the optical layer is becoming more and more dynamic with added intelligence in the management and allocation of wavelength resources, the single layer (typically IP) planning problem becomes also a multi-layer (IP-Optical) problem, since the changes in one layer directly affect the other. In the multilayer problem, some aspects presented in the previous paragraph are changed and presented next. It is noted that here we consider IP over WDM; for IP over OTN over WDM the basic principles remain the same, considering that the switching intelligence is in the OTN layer and the WDM offers only the resources for end-to-end optical connections.

- **Service/Traffic demands.** The service demands of the IP layer define, which are the WDM (Optical) demands in the optical layer. This means that if we want a directed IP/MPLS flow from router 1 to router 2, this requires a lambda in the optical layer from the optical cross connect 1 to the optical cross connect 2. However, the operator sells WDM service too, so the traffic matrix demand in the lower layer can be a composition of the IP demands and the WDM services.
- **Network Equipment.** As we focus on IP over WDM, the planning tool requires to know the interconnection between the IP and the optical equipment. For instance, in previous example about the demand, it is mandatory to know whether router 1 is connected to the optical cross-connect 1 to map the IP demand in the optical layer.
- **Objective.** The objective can be different depending on the layer or an overall objective like cost minimization can be considered.

- **Planning module.** The planning module must support the cross layer mapping of the services, the network equipment as well as the network configuration. It may imply a loopback process to update the IP layer solution in order to re-optimize the optical layer.
- **Network configuration.** The network configuration considers as output both the IP and the optical equipment. With the loopback process the optical layer can be dynamically re-optimized in order to accommodate the changes in the IP layer.

In Section 1.4 we provide a survey of the recent work in multi-layer optimization, with the goal to investigate which, if any, of the existing work can be applied to ACINO. We find that no previous research is directly applicable to ACINO, however, some general ideas and specific schemes are partly applicable, after certain modifications and adjustment. Primarily, the concept of the re-use of existing network resources (routes in the network) is a common theme in literature. In addition, some of the work shows the basic actions that the network may take after receiving a connection request. The survey has also led to the discovery of the simulation tool (Net2Plan), which will be discussed in detail in Section 6.1.

1.3 Application centric network planning

In this section we discuss a flavour of network planning that is particular to ACINO, i.e., the application centric approach. A description of the ACINO approach to planning is given in the “Technical Annex” document of the project, and is refined in this Section.

The ACINO project proposes a novel network planning approach that extends significantly the latest developments (as investigated in Section 1.4) in multi-layer resource optimization, by introducing the “application centric multi-layer planning, online optimization and resource allocation” concept. According to this concept the resource allocation process is performed based on the requirements set by the applications. The purpose is to develop methods and algorithms that allow different IP and optical layer resource allocation mechanisms to jointly orchestrate and optimize the IP and optical layers based on the service requirements set by the applications. For example, specific latency-sensitive applications can be classified and distinguished from the rest of the traffic and served on a delay minimization basis. We will address latency and latency-aware resource allocation specifically in our investigation in Section 4.2.

Figure 1.2 compares the approach taken in ACINO for network planning vs. today's approach (approach I) and the most advanced multi-layer approach (approach II) suggested in [1]. As shown, today's approach is based on separate planning of the IP and optical layers in a three-step process, while approach II attempts to co-optimize both layers in one step. This enables meaningful efficiencies – above 10% in real networks. The ACINO approach also co-optimizes both layers together, like approach II, but based on the actual needs of the applications, which will allow to achieve even better efficiencies by dimensioning the network to meet the application needs.

Figure 1.2: ACINO approach vs previous approaches in network planning

It should be noted here that the term “planning” has been used in the most general sense, i.e. provisioning for requested connections at any time. However, as will be noted in the survey work, in network design there exist several types of planning. Each of these solves a different design problem, the distinguishing dimension being time. Thus, in *offline planning*, the goal is to optimize the network design before the network starts its operation. The traffic that the network will carry is known ahead of time, and there is sufficient time to compute an optimal design. By contrast, in *in-operation planning*, the traffic (often referred to as *dynamic traffic*) is not known initially, and the network must serve connection demands as they come in, in some cases with some advance announcement. The lack of knowledge presents a difficult optimization problem, which has not been covered in great quantity in recent research (see Section 1.4). The resulting network may thus not be as optimal as it would be if the planner had complete advance knowledge of the traffic. This leads to a third type of planning, *online planning*, where existing connections are changed to enable the network to operate more efficiently. In the time dimension, online planning falls between offline and in-operation planning: it is performed neither before the network becomes operational, nor after every connection request, but periodically or when initialized by a request.

The ACINO approach to resource allocation is focused on in-operation planning. This is justified given the unexpected and diverse nature of the service requirements, and the expected highly responsive nature of future networks. However, offline planning is not excluded, as the network should not be expected to start operating with no provisioning at all. Finally, the mentioned sub-optimal network design resulting from in-operation planning will be corrected by means of online planning.

1.4 Existing work

The survey here encompasses the publications mostly from the years 2010-2016. The key word here is “multi-layer”, and was used to perform the search in mostly IEEE conference proceedings and journals. The primary goal is to examine what approaches can be reused, partially or wholly, in ACINO. Comments to the usability of the work in ACINO will thus be made where appropriate. The results of the survey were published in [2].

First, a classification is provided, followed by the identification of the areas of study that are likely to attract more interest. Finally, we suggest a novel objective of future studies.

Optical networks today are organized as two- or three-layer structures. The upper layer is a virtual network usually running IP or MPLS protocols. The lower layer is the optical layer. The virtual network (often referred to as the IP/MPLS layer or simply IP layer) is the electronic layer, which passes packet-encapsulated user data to the optical layer. The optical layer handles the physical aspects of the optical network, such as modulation and demodulation, and error detection and correction. In between these two layers is often a third, namely the Optical Transport Network layer. OTN is utilized for its features such as framing, grooming and strong forward error correction.

The optical network layers have very distinctive characteristics and challenges in terms of design and operation. In this survey we focus on the design aspects. Traditionally the layers are designed as separate entities, which simplifies the problem. On the other hand, simultaneous design of all the layers offers potential benefits, such as better failure detection and traffic protection, and network cost reduction.

An illustration of the different approaches to optical network design is well-illustrated in [3][4] and given below in Figure 1.3. Approach I, commonly used by network operators, allows for simplicity in the design by optimizing each layer separately, but runs the risk of computing a solution that is far from optimal. Approach II is similar, with the difference that the failure analysis is more integrated in the IP layer design step. Finally, Approach III aims to find the best solution possible by designing both the IP and optical layers with one step, assuming that the computational complexity is not too high and that the network designer has access to both the IP and the optical layers. Note that the failures are now accounted for in the single design step, as opposed to in the IP layer only in Approaches I and II. Such a holistic approach is in [3][4] rewarded with a notable reduction in network costs.

Recent literature provides other perspectives on network planning. In [24] network design is explained as a loop-based iterative process that continuously goes through various stages, including traffic measurements as feedback, and changes the network to support the evolving traffic matrix. Another view, with practical constraints such as the temperature ranges and aging margins of optical links, is shown in [37]. As will be shown later, other than the optimization approach, the recent work in multi-layer network design varies in several other ways. Additionally, the industry is looking for ways to exploit multi-layer control commercially [6]. We are thus motivated to look into the state of the art of multi-layer networking. This paper encompasses the publications mostly from the years 2010-2016.

Figure 1.3: Network optimization approaches [3]

1.4.1 Classification

Although multi-layer network design is a common theme, the work surveyed in the next section covers a diverse set of problems and solutions. Thus some authors consider IP-over-WDM networks only, while others introduce OTN as a third layer. To other authors still, IP (or MPLS) is not even explicitly mentioned, and the client layer to the optical is referred to as virtual. The solution to a network design problem may mean designing each of the two (or three) layers separately or together, where the latter usually means using one algorithm to solve the stated problem for both layers. The type of output from the solution of the multi-layer algorithm varies greatly, from only lightpath routes on a given fiber-link network to a complete specification that includes router-to-optical-switch connections, number of ports for each router, spectrum allocation, etc.

Table 1.2 (shown below, after the classification) classifies the work based on several classes. Note that a quantitative classification is not possible, due to the high diversity of the problems and solutions offered in the papers. We now explain the classes in some detail:

Layered technologies – denotes the protocols used in the network models. MPLS is denoted as IP for brevity. Some papers consider the use of optical layer techniques and equipment such as sliceable spectrum and transponders to allow the connections to have a finer granularity than the conventional 50 GHz-based networks. This can result in network cost savings. Additionally, the cost of a link can depend on the layer in which resides. This then presents an optimization problem where special care is taken to select the layer to carry the traffic in order to minimize the total cost.

To coordinate different network layers, a network may utilize Software Defined Networking (SDN). In [5] it is argued that SDN can centralize network control and thus allow for better operation of a running network. The need for SDN in IP-over-optical networks is elaborated in more detailed in [7]. The authors note that it is both feasible and necessary to employ SDN to increase the efficiency and reduce costs in multi-layer networks. However, there remains a need for some functions to remain local, such as fast reaction to failures of network components. This is especially true when one considers the SDN controller as a single point of failure. A further exploration of SDN in multi-layer and multi-domain networks is in [8].

Finally, the most recent published material emphasizes the potential and need for SDN [36][40][41]. Here, SDN is seen as necessary to accomplish multi-layer coordination in practice. After the demonstration of SDN-supported multi-layer connection restoration, the next likely step to commercial viability is the standardization of SDN.

Considers power – indicates that an objective in the study is to minimize the energy that the network will consume. This will be discussed more in a separate section.

Considers physical impairments – indicates that the inputs to network design are variables such as optical reach, i.e. the maximum distance to which an optical signal can be transmitted without regeneration. This consideration stems from the fact that regenerators are expensive. Similarly, regenerating by means of converting the signal to electronic and back to optical introduces a delay. Such a processing delay can easily be comparable or greater than the delay from light propagation. This consideration thus makes for a more realistic network model.

Deals with failures and protection – an optical network should be provisioned so that it reacts to the inevitable failures of its components, both hardware (such as IP router ports, and fiber-links) and software (such as bugs in router software). Taking this into account, some of the surveyed papers provision their networks with mechanisms and redundancy to prevent or mitigate the loss of traffic. This will be discussed more in a separate section.

Optimization method – to solve the optimization problem, the author may use Integer (or Mixed Integer) Linear Programming or a heuristic. The former guarantees an optimal solution but is usually inapplicable to larger-sized networks (beyond about 5-10 nodes). The latter is thus often resorted to, and in some works compared to the ILP solution (for smaller networks) to prove feasibility. Some works do not use ILP at all, and instead show the feasibility of their solutions in other ways, such as comparing their network design to less intelligent but intuitive ones.

Input traffic type – the traffic that a network must carry can be specified as single or a set of matrices that specify the amount of traffic for each node pair. The network may thus be required to merely support the entire traffic matrix at once (static), or support the connection requests as they arrive over time (dynamic). In the latter case, the inherent difficulty is in not knowing in advance how much traffic needs to be supported. Consequently, network planning can be quite different for the two cases. Several papers consider static traffic where the demands are handled sequentially, and claim that this is akin to a dynamic situation. This will be discussed more in a separate section.

Optimization approach – As noted in the introduction, the network designer may decide to consider each layer separately or together with one integrated procedure. An example study showing the added computational complexity required by the integrated approach is [9]. There it is shown that the integrated approach can result in better optimality, but with increased computational complexity. Although the complexity increase can be almost 50%, the actual runtimes were in both cases on the order of only tens of milliseconds.

Table 1.1 classifies the approaches with respect to the layered technologies.

Table 1.1: Joint classification of layered technologies and optimization approaches

IP/WDM and IP/OTN/WDM	one-layer	[27][31][42]
	multi-layer	[3][4][9][10][11][12][13][14][15][16][19][20][22][23][24][25][27][29][37][38][39][43][47]
	one- and multi-layer	[9][12]
IP/elastic	one-layer	[17]
	multi-layer	[16][18][28][30][43]

Table 1.2: Classification of the surveyed work

Layered technologies	IP/WDM	[3][4][9][10][11][12][13][14][15][16][23][24][25][27][26][30][31][38][39][42][43][47]
	IP/elastic	[16][17][18][28][30][43]
	IP/OTN/WDM	[19][20]
	other	[5][7][8][12][21][32][33][34][35]
Considers power		[28][29][30][38][39]
Considers physical impairments		[3][4][16][17][22][23][30][43][47]
Deals with failures and protection		[3][4][24][10][11][27][26][12][33]
Optimization method	ILP	[14][15][30][43]
	heuristics	[3][4][8][9][13][16][18][25][27][26][28][29][33][34][38][47]
	ILP and heuristics	[17][19][20][22][23][24][32][39][42]
	analytics	[11][35]
Input traffic type	static	[8][10][11][13][14][15][16][17][18][19][20][24][25][27][26][28][29][30][31][33][34][35][38][42][39][43][47]
	dynamic	[9][21][22][23][26]
Optimization approach	one-layer	[17][26][31][33]
	multi-layer	[3][4][5][7][8][11][13][14][15][16][18][19][20][22][24][25][10][27][28][29][30][32][34][35][38][39][42][43][47]
	one- and multi-layer	[9][12]
Optimization objective	network cost	[3][4][10][11][14][15][16][17][18][19][20][22][23][24][27][30][33][42][43][47]
	power	[28][29][30][38][39]
	spectrum utilization	[13][27][35]
	other	[8][9][13][27][31][34]

Note that the majority of the papers can be considered to have a multi-layer approach to network design. This is understandable, given that the optimization algorithm is less likely to find a sub-optimal solution due to the two- or three-step procedure as in Approaches I and II in Figure 1.3. However, it should be noted that from the point of view of a network operator, there is value in simplicity of network design and operation. For example, removing the MPLS layer from the network stack may reduce the effort to configure and maintain the network [10][12], assuming the network does not need the features of MPLS such explicit, unconstrained routing.

Optimization objective – this is a key component of network design and simulation, because it affects the optimization methods and the results. The authors consider a variety of quantifiable objectives, sometimes two or more in the same study. Most often, the objective is minimizing the network cost, i.e. values such as connection blocking probability, equipment cost, number of wavelengths, link utilization, and power consumption. In the surveyed work, cost is used to prove that a particular network design method is feasible, rather than show an estimate in currency.

1.4.2 Current and future trends

We have identified some trends in the surveyed work that may continue to be explored further in the future. In this section we also propose a new area of interest that is currently missing from the applications of multi-layer networking.

Dynamic traffic matrix

As shown earlier, most of the classified papers use static traffic matrices as input. In reality, user applications may request connections at any points in time, as opposed to all at once. Similarly, when the user is done using the network service, the connection should be taken down, which may also occur at any time. A common term for user connection request is reservations, which are classified in detail in [21]. Reservations may thus be slotted and unslotted, immediate and advanced, etc., all of which can have an impact on how the network accommodates the requests. A rare paper that explicitly studies scheduled connections, i.e. reservations, with random traffic rates is [22]. The authors assume random traffic rates for the reservations and apply a tabu search heuristic to optimize their IP-over-WDM network design. The result shows that, with a particular cost model, reusing transponders can provide cost savings in a multi-layer network model.

However, the application of multi-layer networking in dynamic traffic is not yet fully explored. This is perhaps surprising, given that accommodating a request for a connection has different implications in different layers. For example, the setup time for an optical connection can be on the order of tens of seconds or minutes, whereas IP or MPLS times can be used much shorter. This, together with the type of service that is requested, may have an impact on network optimization and present an interesting research problem.

Survivability

Here we discuss the works that explicitly consider survivability as a network feature, which is not the case with most of the papers summarized so far. In [23] network services are divided to IP and “wavelength”

(WL), where the WL services are optically protected. In order not to waste the bandwidth of the optically protected services, the authors propose using the bandwidth to carry IP traffic even before a failure. Then, in the event of a failure, WL services enjoy the optical protection, while the IP traffic is shifted onto surviving IP links in the network. Naturally, this requires additional wavelengths to be reserved for the IP traffic in case of a failure.

The above strategy to reuse the existing network resources is also present in [24]. The authors there use a commercial tool and a greedy steepest descent algorithm to design the IP network. Such an approach cannot guarantee network design optimality. However, the paper also demonstrates interesting techniques for restoration after a failure, both in the IP and the optical layer. The overall goal is to avoid using additional capacity to protect the traffic, and instead e.g. use different ports on the routers facing the failure. This is then demonstrated to result in network cost savings on some real network topologies.

Still another approach to multi-layer survivability is in [25]. The authors compare a network that has duplicate core nodes with one that has optical restoration. The latter is termed a “joint approach”, and establishes a new lightpath that avoids the point of failure. This provides cost savings compared to the duplicate node strategy.

In [10] the focus is on IP Fast Reroute (IP FRR), which is a protection scheme that allows the IP layer to protect the traffic with the same delay time (up to 50 ms) as is normally possible in the optical layer. An IP-over-WDM network design with IP FRR protecting half the traffic is shown to require little extra cost compared to a network that has only the relatively slow IP restoration as the protection mechanism. Note that the nature of the IP FRR scheme is also one of reusing the paths through the network whenever possible.

The same authors in [11] explore IP FRR in a network core where the nodes are paired, while the access nodes have links to both nodes in a pair. Seemingly contrary to [25], the results make a case for duplicate nodes. However, the type of traffic protection here is different (fast reroute instead of optical restoration), as is the network model (completely connected IP topology), making the two studies less directly comparable. This example illustrates our point about the diversity of research in multi-layer networking, as the two papers here have a similar idea but differ in the proposed solution.

Similar work on IP FRR is in [26]. Here the goal is to protect the traffic from as many source-destination pairs as possible, using ECMP routes as alternates in case of failure. The results show that about 98% of the pairs can have their traffic protected, while the cost in extra wavelengths is modest. The few quantifiable studies performed so far on IP FRR in a multi-layer setting show that the mechanism is feasible from the cost point of view.

Survivability in both layers is also studied in [27], where the goal is to protect multicast traffic. To ensure survivability, access links are dual-homed to the core routers, while the core uses optical protection. A heuristic based on simulated annealing is used to optimize the network design. The numerical results show that multicast outperforms running many unicasts instead.

A question that has not been received a definite answer in any of the surveyed papers is which layer should be used to protect the traffic against failures, given that each layer has its own protection capabilities. For example, even though either layer can reroute the traffic in 50 ms, the advantage of the optical is that the failure does not have to be reported to the IP layer, thus avoiding unwanted recomputation of IP routes. However, in situations where path restoration is needed, the IP layer can restore the traffic more quickly. In all cases, a design problem can be formulated so that the network trades the desirable traffic protection features for a minimum investment.

Power consumption

Power consumption of telecommunications networks is deemed a major contributor to adverse effects on the environment [38][39]. Thus, in recent years, power has become a component in network optimization, and there are research efforts to design networks whose use of energy is minimized. This usually requires minimizing the number of lightpaths used, which in turn allows for IP router ports to be turned off to save energy. IP routers and ports, rather than optical switches, consume the most power in optical networks.

In [28] the authors propose a network where traffic is monitored at the ingress point to determine if the required Quality of Service is met. If it is not, traffic is moved between different “QoS slices” until the desired QoS is achieved. Simultaneously, an algorithm is proposed to minimize the number of lightpaths used in the network, the ultimate goal being the shutting down of unused router ports. This then provides energy savings.

A different approach, but with the same objective, is offered in [29]. Here careful traffic grooming is applied to maximize the amount of traffic on each lightpath, thus minimizing the number of lightpaths. This in turn reduces the number of IP ports needed to carry the traffic. In other words, since optical switch ports consume far less power than IP router ports, the strategy is to route the traffic in the optical layer as much as possible. In addition, the lightpaths traversing the same fiber links are merged and switched together to provide further energy savings.

The idea of preferably optical routing is further emphasized in [38], which is an improvement over [39]. The optimization algorithm accommodates one connection request at a time, and each time changes the routing of the previously established lightpaths so as to minimize the total power consumption.

In [30] the authors evaluate IP-over-elastic networks, with equipment costs and energy as (separate) optimization objectives. The simulated equipment includes bandwidth variable transponders (BVTs), sliceable BVTs, and flex-grid switches, as well as the more traditional fixed-grid switches and fixed line rate transponders. To calculate the cost, the authors assume a particular yearly traffic increase and equipment type costs to simulate the network on the Deutsche Telekom topology. The simulations demonstrate an advantage of flex-grid switches. BVTs are shown to be more efficient at high traffic loads, while the sliceable BVTs are more useful at low traffic loads, i.e. the early years.

To summarize, similar to the survivability studies, power-aware proposals call for reusing the existing network resources, which, due to the high energy consumption of the electronic components, translates to aggregating the traffic onto few optical lightpaths.

1.4.3 Proposed future work

One continuation of the work in multi-layer optical networking, but with a different flavour, would be research that binds the technical and economic aspects of optical networks. It has now been the case for several years that much of the revenue in networking is generated by higher network layer entities such as search engines and content providers, rather than the providers of telecommunication services. The research community has responded with suggestions to reduce capital and operational costs, but little attention has been given to how to maximize the revenue from the offered services. Careful consideration of the choice of the layers in which to provide the service, as well as pricing the service correctly, may thus offer a chance to increase network revenue.

This selection of layers, routes, and other resources can be coupled with pricing negotiation. (Note that the ideas discussed in the publications aim to reduce the network cost solely through technological optimization, i.e. finding an optimum set of lightpaths, the minimum number of IP ports, the best spectrum allocation, etc.). Negotiation can be thus used as a refined admission tool, by motivating the application to scale down or scale up its required parameters. The network monitors its remaining resources and adjusts the pricing accordingly, the end result being a maximized revenue. The benefit on the application side is that it will receive the best service for the price. Variations of such a scheme may become relevant with the advent of digital markets, where optical networks are required to support a multitude of customers, providers, and services.

Thus, for high speed networks whose purpose is to generate a net profit, our recommendation is that future studies of multi-layer network design and operations take the service income, rather than just expenses, into account.

1.4.4 Summary of the existing work

Grouping the recent work requires many classes, and in some cases the studies in the same group differ from each other by method, objective or conclusion. The survey thus shows that considering multiple layers is not the goal, but rather the means to efficient networking. The main reward is savings (in cost, power, wavelengths, etc.), which may be traded off for the added complexity of dealing with multiple layers simultaneously. The distribution of papers shows that joint optimization, where both the electronic and optical layers are designed with the same method, dominates the recent work. To that end, most authors employ heuristic optimization due to its scalability versus ILP, and its ability to handle complex network models versus analytics. There is yet no common tool for multi-layer network optimization, although there are efforts underway [44][45].

We have shown the areas of multi-layer networking application that are likely to be continued to be explored. First, power reduction aims to reduce the energy consumed by telecommunication networks primarily in the electronic layer. The common theme to all the surveyed papers here is turning off unneeded IP ports, which consume by far the most energy in a network. This goal can be achieved by careful traffic grooming, optical bypass lightpath routing, reusing the existing lightpaths, and merging the lightpaths to switch them together. All these techniques then minimize the number of IP ports in the

network. Although a study explores elastic networks, most of the interest is in WDM, which may be understandable due to the opportunities to aggregate the traffic and reuse the lightpaths in WDM.

Second, survivability is a recurring topic in current research. This is understandable because there exists a number of methods to protect the traffic (optical and IP restoration, 1+1 optical protection, IP and MPLS FRR), each with different properties. While some proposals utilize only one layer for protection, the most interesting works utilize both electronic and optical. Note that, although multi-layer survivability studies have existed for years, their practicability is being demonstrated only now that SDN has offered a chance to centralize network control.

Third, the challenge of dynamic traffic in IP-over-optical networks, despite some efforts is far from being fully explored. A look into multi-layer network design principles that are optimal with respect to a sequence of connection requests may thus be warranted. A project to address this is in progress [46].

The study further shows that two of the identified themes, power consumption minimization and survivability, in some cases share a common strategy that is IP port reuse. However, in survivability studies the motivation is to minimize the network cost, avoid depleting the IP layer resources, protect (part of) the traffic, or reduce the outage time, whereas the power saving schemes primarily aim to reduce the consumption. The idea to reuse the existing resources is also present in the small amount of work performed on dynamic traffic.

Finally, we have proposed a different area of study, where multi-layer intelligence may provide a way to contribute on the revenue side of network operations. We believe that this problem will become more relevant as customers and networks become connected into digital markets of multiple service providers. A network design will then have a chance to balance revenue against expenditures (in terms of cost and energy), and negotiation against admission while ensuring network serviceability.

2 Reference network

A complete description of the reference network is given in D2.1, so in this Section we give only a brief overview. We expose only the details of the network that are relevant to task 3.3.

The reference network consists of the access, metro and backbone segments. For the ACINO project, and specifically for task 3.3, the most relevant segment is the backbone, which consist of a core and a regional network. In both of those, both the IP and optical technologies are employed, thus providing an opportunity for application-centric multi-layer optimization.

The core IP network consist of fourteen routers and the links between them. The topology is divided in to parts, where each part consists of seven routers and their links, so that two core routers are in each region. There are links between the routers in the same region, but these are only used for protection. Access routers in each region are dual-homed on the two core routers.

The underlying core optical network consists of thirty optical routers and the fibre-links between them. Since there are only fourteen IP routers, not all routers have a co-located optical switch; conversely, some optical switches are not directly connected to an IP router. However, the optical fibre network is quite meshy and thus provides opportunity for diverse lightpath routing, which in turn can result in good load balancing and choices for backup path routing. Illustrations of the core network topologies are given in Section 6.2.2, where the topologies are used to produce preliminary quantitative evaluation of network allocation strategies.

In addition to the IP and optical topologies, the reference network has fiber-link lengths (in kilometres), and an excel spread sheet showing the end-to-end traffic volumes (in Gb/s) between core IP routers.

3 Definition of the overall application aware resource allocation and optimization process

The ACINO planning strategies refer to the required processes for the optimized allocation of the network resources across the IP and Optical layer, according to the generated demands and the application-related requirements (i.e. the service requirements). The strategies also define the actions that will be taken by the orchestrator for the re-optimization of the network which includes the cases of network failures.

This section defines the adopted procedures for the resource provisioning and optimization modules including the flow of information between the NBI and SBI modules. The specific strategies for the resource allocation and optimization modules are described separately in the following two sections, 4 and 5, of this deliverable.

3.1 The multi-layer provisioning and planning modules in the ACINO Orchestrator

The multi-layer resource allocation and optimization modules (see highlighted part in Figure 3.1) are centrally located in the ACINO orchestrator. The Multi-Layer Provisioning Module (MLP-M) implements the application aware multi-layer routing and resource allocation algorithms, for each service request that is received by the Intent/Primitive Framework Module through the intent translator. The Online Planning Tool Module (OPT-M) includes all the supporting actions for the re-optimization of the network in real time, as well as for the calculation of the network status and resources for scheduled services.

Figure 3.1: The ACINO orchestrator architecture. The MLP-M and OPT-M are highlighted.

The above-described modules implement the required algorithms for the dynamic resource allocation and resource optimization functions according to the specific strategies defined in this deliverable in sections 4 and 5. Moreover, according to the adopted ACINO orchestrator architecture, the Multi-Layer Provisioning and Online Planning Tool Modules interface with the NBI (through the Intent/Primitive Framework Module), the SBIs (through the Transaction Handler Module and Abstraction Layer Modules) and the databases. The communication among the modules (i.e. the module interfaces) are implemented following the interfacing rules defined in WP4 T4.2 and T4.3.

3.2 Overall procedure and flow of information after a demand arrives

The basic steps that will be followed when an application demand (i.e. an intent) is generated are described in general below:

1. An application by a customer appears and expresses its “intents” to the NBI module.

The exact definition of what an application needs to express to the NBI will be finalized in D3.2. NBI translates the intent (through an intent engine) to network service requirements. Network service requirements are specific and quantifiable network parameters that are adopted in order to successfully serve the intent as, for example: list of end-to-end logical connections, type of connection (bidirectional, mesh etc.), bandwidth (10, 40G, adaptive), end-to-end delay (<100ms), protection type (IP only), recovery time, scheduling, etc. The best current definition for the specific set of requirements can be found in D2.1, Section 2.4.

2. The MLP-M receives the network service requirements and calculates the optimum network resource allocation to the application, based on a set of rules (i.e. heuristics) per application and the current topology information by the databases.

This is the core of the resource allocation activity and refers to the default online (dynamic) case that deals with the allocation of the connections with certain service requirements. The computation process for the optimum online allocation is defined in Section 4. As an additional step, the OPT-M re-optimizes periodically or on demand the network resources. Typically, this is an offline planning and resource (re)optimization process and is presented in Section 5.

3. The orchestrator sets up the computed connection(s) via the IP and optical controllers.

The computed IP routes and optical paths for each connection are passed to the controllers via the appropriate ONOS [55] interfaces. In turn the controllers reserve the resources and set-up the end-to-end connections over the data plane.

4. Network data bases are updated.

The status and topology information for both layers is constantly updated after a successful establishment of a connection or when a failure is monitored. This is discussed in more details in Section 3.5.

3.3 Interfacing with the Intent/Primitive Framework Module (NBI)

3.3.1 Application intents translation into service requirements

An intent translation engine is included inside the Intent/Primitive Framework Module and is responsible to translate the intents (i.e. the demands coming from different applications) into service requirements. The service requirements are in the form of simple network level parameters for the requested logical end-to-end connections, as reported in Section 3.2.

3.3.2 Accommodating the translated intents

The Intent/Primitive Framework Module provides service requirements to the optimization modules in the form of lists. A list example is reported below:

1. Latency 20 ms, Bandwidth 300 Gb/s, IP protection
2. Latency 30 ms, Bandwidth 300 Gb/s, IP protection
3. Latency 30 ms, Bandwidth 300 Gb/s, no protection

The service requirements specified in each element of such a list are enough to satisfy the intent. Moreover, the elements of the list are not dependent on each other, so accommodating one is sufficient to satisfy the intent coming from the application. However, the list is prioritized. Consequently, the optimization module attempts to accommodate the service requirements in the first entry. If this is successful, a connection is established and a positive feedback is sent to the upper modules. If this fails, the optimization modules attempt the next element in the list. If no attempt is successful, a negative feedback is sent to the upper modules. The detailed data format for the service requirements will be reported in D3.4 and later implemented for D4.3.

3.4 Interfacing with the IP and Optical layer controllers (SBI)

The outcome of the multi-layer optimization is received by the lower modules in the ACINO architecture. The optimization modules (Multi-Layer Provisioning and Online Planning Tool Modules) must provide enough data for the IP and optical controllers to establish a connection, i.e., the route that must be followed in the IP and optical layers. Note that explicit routing is needed in both layers to accommodate the applications' intents separately. Thus, for the optical layer, the optimization module will provide a list of fiber-links that the lightpaths will traverse, as well as the spectrum needed to carry such lightpaths. Instead, in the IP layer, the set of IP links to be traversed will be provided. Note that, since explicit routing is needed and IP cannot support it, MPLS is required to work in conjunction with IP.

The data format for the output of the optimization modules, that is given as input to the IP and optical controllers, will be examined in detail in D3.4 and D4.3. The format will depend on the capabilities and requirements of the ONOS orchestrator, which has been chosen as platform to develop the ACINO orchestrator. In fact, the optimization modules will communicate with the controllers via ONOS. It should also be noted that the open source nature and the flexibility of the Net2Plan optimizer, that has been chosen as tool for the development of the optimization modules and will be thoroughly investigated in Section 6.1, should allow for most any output format. Similarly, due to its high flexibility, it should also be possible for Net2Plan to take any data format as input.

3.5 Interfacing with the Network State and Inventory Database

The Network State and Inventory Database (NSDB) maintains an updated status of the network topology over both the IP and Optical layers. The multi-layer optimization algorithms recall the topology information from the database for their calculations. A more precise definition of the network database is given in D3.1.

The optimization modules should not update the NSDB after finding a route, since that route may be unavailable and the optimization module does not know it. Instead the NSDB update is performed by the lower modules, which have the most updated view about newly allocated resources and failures. The optimization module then gathers the needed information from NSDB before performing the optimization. It is also updated by the Controller/SBI with respect to the last requested demands for connectivity (e.g. “requested lightpath approved and set up”, “IP link (A,F) is up”, etc.). Meanwhile, the optimization module reserves the newly (online) computed resources until they have been confirmed by the Controller, so as not to be assigned to another connection request.

The flow of the network state information is important in order to avoid inconsistencies and resource allocation miscalculations. This is discussed in the following paragraph.

3.6 Dealing with network view inconsistencies

A change in the network may result in an inaccurate computation of the resources. A good example of this is a failure that is not reported on time to the optimization modules. Then the module will compute a connection over a link or port that is not functioning. The request for the connection will be passed to the IP and/or optical controllers, but the request will not be completed. We propose two ways to deal with the optimization modules’ obsolete network view:

1. In case of a failure, notify the optimization module. This implies that the optimization module maintains its own view of the network state, and updates it upon receiving the post-failure update from the SBI. However, in addition to requiring a copy of the network state, this requires that the SBI notification be quick and complete; any change in the network must be reported and a data structure for such an update be defined.
2. A simpler way is to avoid maintaining a database in the optimization modules, and instead read the view of the network every time an application request arrives. This assumes that the network view can be received by the optimization module quickly, ideally on the order of seconds or milliseconds, so as avoid using an obsolete view. However, note that the optimization module will likely have to maintain a record of the established connections, which will naturally require a view of the network. Therefore, the previous option may be more practical.

In either case, the optimization module will have to be notified by the Controllers if the request for a connection was a success or a failure. In case of a failure, the optimization module will update its view of the network, because the failure was presumably caused by an obsolete view of the network. Then the optimization will be started again, and eventually a new connection request sent down to the lower modules.

In order to choose best procedure for dealing with network view inconsistencies, we will want to know more about the capabilities of the ONOS orchestrator, i.e., what notifications it can provide, what details about the network can be received, etc., as well as the time scale for each notification. These details will become clearer as work progresses into tasks 3.4 and later 4.3.

4 Multi-layer routing and resource allocation processes

This section describes the adopted strategies for the development of the application aware multi-layer resource allocation algorithm, implemented in the Multi-Layer Provisioning Module (MLP-M). It is noted that the same algorithm and the overall strategy is also used by the Online Planning Tool Module (OPT-M), described in section 5, where it is expanded in order to meet certain optimization criteria.

4.1 Mapping of service requirements to multi-layer network resources

The mapping process defines the main resource allocation strategy that is followed in ACINO and is based on the algorithms originally proposed in [48] and later assessed in [49]. The resources are identified separately for the two layers, the IP and Optical layers. However, the mapping process is performed jointly by considering the optimum allocation of the available resources. This process is based on priorities with respect to the selection of the resources, while the priorities depend on the type of application and its needs (through the application driven service requirements that are generated).

In each layer there are two actions that can be performed:

- Reuse of existing IP route and/or lightpath OR
- Set-up of a new IP route and/or lightpath

In general, the reuse action leads to faster allocation of connections and better economics but lacks the added flexibility and global optimization features, which are achieved with the set-up action.

The available combinations of the above actions lead to 4 possible operations with respect to the provisioning of the application demands that can be then prioritised according to the needs of the applications through the generated service requirements. These are:

1. Use of an existing (single-hop) IP link between the source and the destination (Option 1, **Opt1**)
2. Use of an existing (multi-hop) IP route between the source and the destination (Option 2, **Opt2**)
3. Set up of a new (single-hop) IP link between the source and the destination, which denotes the set-up of an optical path between source and destination, (Option 3, **Opt3**)
4. Set up of an additional IP link to an existing IP route, which denotes the set-up of an optical link or path that extends an already established (single- or multi-hop) IP link covering part of the requested end-to-end connection, (Option 4, **Opt4**)

The four options are illustrated in the example of Figure 4.1 considering a demand that requests connection between nodes A and D.

Figure 4.1: Example of the four demand allocation options for a connectivity request between A and D. The illustrated nodes are routers, while the optical layer elements are not shown. The black lines refer to the already established IP connections and the green lines refer to new IP connections.

The original idea of the adopted multi-layer planning strategy (if one follows the allocation options in the order they appear above) is the following: When a new demand arrives we try first to allocate it over a directed existing IP link or an existing IP route, thus fully utilizing the existing resources and saving in cost and lightpath installation time. If no IP link or route is found, then we either establish a new optical link directly between the end-to-end nodes, while if no optical resources are available to do that then we extend an already established IP route to reach the final destination. In this scheme the first two options deal only with the IP layer resources while the optical layer resources come into play only when no IP layer resources are available.

For the needs of the ACINO project, the application awareness concept must be introduced to the above multi-layer allocation options. This is done by defining a set of allocation strategies (detailed next in Section 4.2), which depend on the type of the application demands and on the associated service requirements. As a result, for each service requirement, the offered options are prioritised differently. So, for example, if a latency sensitive connection is requested, Opt1 is checked first and if no single-hop link is available then Opt3 is considered to establish one. On contrary, for a best effort type of request, Opt2 is examined first so as to reserve any direct connections for the latency-sensitive applications. Also a typical strategy is the one that separates between IP and Optical protection type of services in conjunction with other requirements like latency, high bandwidth or any special policies. Moreover, the k-shortest paths are calculated for each service requirement in the IP and Optical layer (typically with $K=3$ for national networks). This allows specific requests to be allocated over longer IP links or even optical paths, thus offering both load balancing options (by avoiding congested parts of the network) and optimised resource provisioning, for demanding large bandwidth or low latency service requirements. This strategy essentially activates Opt4 in the allocation process allowing remote optical paths to be set-up to accommodate longer path connections in the IP layer.

Two examples are used in the following to explain the main concept and rational behind the resource allocation strategy concepts:

- Example 1: In a first example we consider only the latency requirements of a service. A preferable strategy denotes to preserve the direct IP link (Opt 1) for highly constrained demands with strict latency requirements, thus applying first Opt 2 for certain demands with relaxed latency requirements. Of course this is true as long as the multi-hop route is longer than a certain number of hops that violates the requested properties. Practically, this means that we calculate and select a longer shortest path for certain applications rather than the available shortest path. In another case, a request for an ultra-low latency connection will first examine Opt 1 and if no direct path is available then Opt 2 is skipped and Opt 3 is examined. However, in this case the demand must be scheduled for a later time since the set-up of a new lightpath requires some time.
- Example 2: The interplay between the IP and Optical layer in the application aware allocation process and for different types of application demands is illustrated in the simple 4-node example of Figure 4.2. The initial state is shown in Figure 4.2a, assuming that 3 bidirectional optical links are already established between IP ports in nodes A-B, B-D and C-D. The arrival of a latency sensitive service

requirement request between A and D (Figure 4.2b) dictates the establishment of an optical path ABD between these nodes, thus generating a direct A-D IP link in the topology. On the contrary, for a best effort connection between A-C (Figure 4.2c), the multi-hop IP route A-B-D-C is preferred as first option in order to reuse the already established optical links and IP ports. In Figure 4.2d a latency sensitive request between A-C requiring optical protection arrives.. In this case, a direct A-C link is established while also an optical path through ABDC nodes is established thus generating the working and protection single hop links between A-C. If instead this request was a high bandwidth connection request between A and C, which could not be served on the existing capacity over the multi-hop A-B-D-C IP route (Figure 4.2e), then again the establishment of a direct A-C link is requested. However, in order to provide IP level protection for this service, the already established A-B-D-C multi-hop link can be considered that carries only best-effort service. In case of a A-C link failure, the high bandwidth IP protected service will switch to the A-B-D-C path while a new request for the best effort service will be generated and examined. A final example (Figure 4.2f) considers a service requirement with moderate latency request of maximum 2 IP hops between A-C. In this case either the direct A-C or the 2-hop A-D-C IP link could be considered which have been established though over the AC and ABDC paths respectively in the optical layer (provided that in each case there is available capacity for this request). If, however, the high bandwidth A-C connection also has rate-adjustable features (e.g. supporting a datacentre migration request), then, the longer A-D-C IP route can be preferred, thus supporting the extra requested feature for the previous request.

Figure 4.2: An application aware planning example over a simple 4-node network

4.2 Implementation of routing constraints in IP-Optical layers

To summarize the four options presented in Section 4.1, to handle a request the network can either reuse existing resources (i.e., IP routes through the network) or allocate new resources (i.e., establishing new lightpaths). The strategy is illustrated in Figure 4.3. The following paragraphs describe the adopted set of

rules, according to our strategy, that define when the resources are reused or new ones are allocated and how these are chosen for different service requirement requests. These rules will be the basis for the heuristics that will implement the ACINO multi-layer application aware algorithms.

4.2.1 Resource reuse and new lightpath allocation strategies

As a starting rule for choosing a route through the network, we will always choose to reuse existing resources first, if possible. The rationale for this is as follows:

- Connection setup time is much shorter than when new resources are allocated. This will be less true once optical networks become completely automatized, however, that will not happen in the near future. The shorter setup time will also support applications that require immediate or near-immediate service from the network. Reusing the existing resources makes the network more responsive, which will become more important in the future, going towards highly programmable and available networks.
- Energy savings. If a lightpath is already available, no extra energy is needed, whereas a new allocation will require new ports in the IP and optical switches and in turn extra energy to power them.

As the first step in the re-use strategy, we will use a path through the IP network if possible. To that end, we describe how to choose the path to take through an existing IP network (Opt1 and Opt2 in Section 4.1). To compute that path, we construct an auxiliary graph, which has the same links and nodes as the network IP topology. Such an approach is common practice in the literature [48][49]. We show an example of such a scheme in [52]. Then, the links that do not have sufficient capacity to meet the bandwidth requested by the connection request are removed from the auxiliary graph. Next, the algorithm adjusts the link weights according to the latency requirement. The goal of this adjustment is to allow the latency-sensitive traffic to use the shortest path through the network, while forcing the less latency-sensitive traffic to take longer paths. The link weights depend on the latency of the IP links, including the lightpaths that implement the IP links, and the service requirement latency. Finally, the shortest path on the weighted auxiliary graph is used to route the traffic.

Otherwise, if no existing path is able to carry the traffic in the IP layer (e.g. the shortest path has latency that is too high), we allocate a new lightpath through the network (Opts 3 and 4 in Section 4.1). By default, we will use *balanced* lightpath routing. This means that an auxiliary graph is constructed starting from the WDM physical network, where for each link (i.e., for each fiber-link) the link weight equals the number of used optical channels traversing the link plus one. The “plus one” addition here is to avoid having many paths with the same length of zero when there are no optical connections in the network. Then a shortest path is found through the auxiliary graph. We follow this strategy for the following reasons:

- A benefit is avoiding a concentration of lightpaths on a small set of fibre-links, which tends to occur with ordinary shortest path lightpath routing.
- This in turn results in fewer IP links that get disconnected after a fibre cut, and less traffic to reroute

- Lightpaths being set up later will not have to face congested links from the previously set up lightpaths
- Because the lightpaths are dispersed through the network, the optical switches require less switching capacity

Because balanced routing penalizes using a small subset of the available fiber-links, new lightpaths will avoid congested fibers, and as a result the lightpaths will be longer than if we were using shortest-hop paths or shortest physical distance paths. This may result in latencies that cannot support latency-sensitive applications. If a particular connection request cannot be satisfied due to a tight latency service requirement, we will establish a lightpath over a shortest physical distance path. In other words, the auxiliary graph will have weights that equal the physical length of the corresponding fiber-links.

To assign wavelengths to the lightpath, we will use the well-known first-fit strategy. Note that, after choosing a lightpath, the algorithm may find insufficient spectrum, so that wavelength assignment cannot be performed successfully. In that case, the algorithm will try the next shortest path. The lightpath routine is thus the well-known K-shortest path algorithm, and apply it in both balanced and shortest-distance routing. If no lightpath is satisfactory, the algorithm returns failure.

While the above steps describe how to set up a lightpath, they do not define the endpoints for the lightpaths. For example, if the endpoints for the requested connections are A and D, we may set up a lightpath directly from A to D (Opt3 in Section 4.1), or, alternatively, a lightpath from A to B, and another from B to D (Opt4 in Section 4.1). To define the lightpath endpoints, we are based on the IP network topology of the reference network (see Section 2 and detailed diagrams in D2.1). This defines the nodes which *may* have an IP link between them, and, conversely, the nodes which *may not* have an IP link connecting them. Next, we show more precisely how to choose the IP links to establish (among those that may be established), and how to establish the lightpaths to implement the IP links.

We will want to establish a shortest-hop path in the IP network. Note that the shortest hop paths in the reference IP topology have one or two hops, so it does not make sense to use the IP layer capacity (e.g. using two instead of one-hop paths) much larger than the required. Note also that the shortest-hop path is not uniquely defined for some node pairs whose shortest paths have two hops in the reference IP network; there are six such pairs. For those cases, there exist two shortest-hop paths. We choose to set up a connection using one or both IP links from and to the central (Madrid region) IP router. The rationale here is that the Madrid IP router will have the hardware (ports, CPU power, etc.) to switch the large amounts of traffic traversing it, so it makes sense to add capacity to the IP links going to Madrid. In addition, future connection requests are likely to be to or from Madrid, so it makes sense to add capacity there and later accommodate the requests quickly, i.e. by “re-using” the connections.

Now, recall that we are setting up new lightpaths, because there was no path available for re-use. It implies that one or more links in the path had insufficient bandwidth or the latency was too long. If it is only the bandwidth that is insufficient, we add capacity to the one or two links in the IP paths that has insufficient capacity. We thus add additional optical channels such that the lightpaths follow the same fiber-links as

before. Adding capacity to existing connections is simpler than setting up a new connection. An additional advantage is that all the packets will experience the same delay. In case there is not enough capacity in the optical layer, we abandon the attempt to expand an IP link and instead set up a new one.

If it is latency that is unsatisfactory instead, for the longer latency lightpath, we set up a new optical connection that has the needed bandwidth and latency. If the total latency is still too long, we do the same for the other lightpath. Finally, if both the bandwidth and the latency are unsatisfactory, we follow the same principle as if only the latency was unsatisfactory.

The strategy outlined above is illustrated in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Diagram showing the basic strategy for resource allocation

4.2.2 Protection and restoration strategy

Here we outline the steps to be taken in our network design so that the network can react to failures of its components and thus protect the traffic. The failures we will protect against are fibre-link cuts, IP port (transceiver) failures, and router failures. Traffic can be protected by both the optical and the IP layer. In

each of the layers, the available mechanisms can be divided into protection (fast) and restoration (slow). Each of the mechanisms has its features and advantages over the other.

Some considerations for the protection strategy are given in D2.1 (Section 4.3). We refine the strategy outlined therein here. As in D2.1, the strategy relies on both the IP and optical layers to protect the traffic. For each application, the chosen protection mechanism depends on the application service requirements. However, in addition to the applications, the protection strategy should depend on the network on which it will be executed, which in our case is the reference network from Section 2. We now examine the reference network to help define the protection strategy.

Note first that the core IP network topology consists of two identical parts (call them planes), each of which consists of a star and a ring. Now, looking at the shortest-hop paths in each plane, we note that the paths have at most two hops. For each two-hop path, there exists another, disjoint two-hop path. For example, if the two-hop path is via the Madrid router (star links), there is an alternate path between the same endpoints in the ring. For each one-hop paths, there is a two-hop alternate path: if the one-hop path is in the star, the alternate is in the ring, and vice-versa. In addition, the IP routers in the same region have an IP connection between them, which is used only for rerouted traffic after failures. Thus, in the event of a failure, traffic can be rerouted from one plane to the other, which provides more backup paths in the IP layer. Finally, in the access part of the network, the access routers are dual-homed on the core routers, so there is a way to protect the traffic from link and router failures there. The alternate paths in the IP layer can thus be considered to have about the same length as the original paths. This property of the IP topology is advantageous for applications that have strict latency requirements.

Another consideration in the IP layer is that, if the topology is severely perturbed due to the re-computation of the routes (IP restoration), traffic will flow unpredictably, which may cause some service requirements to be violated. We thus want to preserve the IP topology and routes after a failure. This leads to the choice of IP protection (IP Fast Reroute), rather than restoration, as the mechanism in the IP layer. This mechanism is fast and will start rerouting the traffic after a few tens of milliseconds, thus satisfying the applications that cannot tolerate a long outage. The applications that can tolerate a longer outage will thus be protected as well; the short outage will not affect them negatively.

The IP layer thus protects the traffic, but only for a limited amount of time. The alternate routes may not have sufficient capacity to carry all the traffic, so some packet may be dropped, thus interrupting the service or lowering its quality. Also, the traffic flows after a failure will result in unbalanced link utilizations. Finally, even the best-effort traffic cannot be stopped indefinitely – the network should support all the applications that it agreed to serve.

The optical layer is invoked here to restore the network: the disconnected lightpaths are re-established over a different set of fibre-links. Note that the messy optical layer topology lends itself to lightpath diversity, so it is expected that alternate paths can be found for any reasonable set of disconnected lightpaths. The alternate lightpath must be carefully considered so that its length satisfies the service requirements of the applications whose data it carries. Thus, similar to the previous section, we attempt to

establish a lightpath using a graph where link weights equal the number of traversing lightpaths (i.e., occupied channels). If this results in a latency requirement violation, we establish a shortest-distance lightpath. If this is unsuccessful, e.g. a lightpath that is short enough cannot be carried, we establish the shortest lightpath that can carry all the required traffic. This way all the traffic will reach its destination, latency-insensitive applications will receive full service, and the latency-sensitive applications will suffer a minimal degradation of service.

The above reasoning highlights the multi-layer nature of the proposed traffic protection strategy. To emphasize it further, note first that any IP layer protection scheme assumes that a fibre-link cut will not simultaneously disconnect both the primary and the backup IP route, which in general is not guaranteed. To address this, note that the balanced lightpath routing strategy described above increases the chance that the primary and the backup route will not have IP links in the same *shared-risk link groups* (SRLGs). Note also that the backup path is subject to service requirements so that after a failure the application will not notice a degradation of the service.

Thus, when computing a new connection, we first attempt to find a suitable backup path in the IP network, which again reflects our preference to re-use the existing network resources. If such path cannot be found, we resort to setting up a new backup path in the same fashion we found the primary, while avoiding the primary path fibre-links. If this cannot be done, we return a failure. Alternatively, both the primary and the backup path (in either layer) can be found together, using the well-known two disjoint paths algorithm. Again, if one of the paths does not satisfy the service requirements (e.g. it is too long to satisfy the latency requirement), we return a failure.

4.2.3 Extended resource allocation strategies to handle flexgrid/elastic optical networks

Flexgrid and elastic systems [58] aim to improve spectral efficiency and allow dynamic adaptation to line-rate changes exploiting sliceable bandwidth variable transceivers (SBVT)s and flexible spectrum allocation, overcoming the limitations imposed by the fixed ITU grid. However, efficiency gains are strongly dependent on the traffic distribution across nodes, which in turn is determined by the routing and traffic aggregation techniques used. Hence, appropriate network planning techniques should be developed in order to maximize the benefits of flexgrid.

When planning is done for an elastic optical network, it is advantageous to change the order in which the requests are considered. Since the higher bit rate transceivers have limited reach, the requests that would be served by them are best searched in increasing path length order, ensuring that as many requests as possible are served using the more spectrally efficient modulation format.

Moreover, spectrum assignment for elastic optical networks is more complicated compared to traditional WDM systems. Even though an elastic system can be handled as a WDM system with a finer grid (typically 12.5 GHz instead of say 50 GHz), the allocations must be done in terms of continuous spectral slots and not as single wavelengths, since the required bandwidth per allocation is no longer fixed but depends on the actual modulation format used and the respective guardband requirements.

The adoption of application awareness in the planning process of a flexgrid optical layer is implemented by keeping track for each request of several parameters. An indicative list follows:

- Maximum allowed path length, which can be used to ensure that the propagation delay is bounded, as well as to ensure that a spectrally efficient modulation format can be used.
- Protection over dedicated paths, to allow 1+1 and 1:1 protection schemes with quick restoration time.
- The option to allow “reverse multiplexing” to split request into multiple smaller ones routed individually, which will allow more efficient packing of the traffic, but will add delay for flow reassembly and is also likely to add jitter.

5 Online planning and optimization processes

The Online Planning Tool Module (OPT-M) has a supporting role to the multi-layer optimization process. This module accommodates all the functions that are related:

- a. With the joint re-optimization process of the network resources
- b. With the execution of operator driven “what-if” scenarios

This section describes the processes handle by the OPT-M. The last part comments on the interfacing requirements of the module with the rest of the modules of the orchestrator and the flow of the information.

5.1 Joint multi-layer re-optimization strategy

The MLP-M, discussed in section 4, provides a resource allocation strategy for new connections according to their service requirements and the available resources at the time that the requests appear. A global optimum is not possible to be maintained for two main reasons: a) The requests during the online process can only be handled in a ‘first come first serve’ basis and b) Connections are released over time, freeing resources (bandwidth, ports, etc.) that may not be the best fit for other demands that appear, leading to some waste of resources (i.e., a problem of resource fragmentation arises).

The OPT-M operates either on a demand basis or on a scheduled basis and is able to identify the best solution for a number of connections, according to their service requirements and the current view of the network resources at the time of calculation. Such process allows certain connections to be reallocated, without though violating their initial service requirements. The overall goal for the re-optimization process is to increase the network performance and reduce its operating cost and power consumption, by freeing resources that can be used by newly assigned connections which are either estimated or scheduled to run in the future.

5.1.1 Multi-layer re-optimization features

Optimization targets

The re-optimization process does not necessary guarantees that a global optimum network state will be reached after the process is concluded. Actually achieving a global optimum would possibly require the reallocation of a very large number of connections which can be an extremely time consuming process, due to the time needed to calculate the global optimum and in particularly due to the time needed for the new optical layer connections to be set-up before the old ones are released.

Instead the adopted strategy focuses on the re-optimization of resources over certain links only, when the resource utilization is reduced. This indicates that a monitoring mechanism is installed that calculates the use of resources in the network as connections are established and released. Flags will be raised when utilization or any other related measure (e.g. fragmentation level in elastic flex-grid networks) exceeds certain levels. The re-optimization process can then be chosen to run for specific connections with the goal to free resources over certain parts of the networks with degraded performance.

Moreover, several optimization goals can be considered. The typical one adopted is to maintain an optimum pool of resources that will allow new connections that are expected or provisioned to be established (see also below the paragraph on Provisioning strategy). Additional goals can consider the reduction of the power consumption or/and the increase of the spectrum utilization at the optical layer.

Targeted duration

The targeted re-optimization process can be essentially completed within a short duration thus having minimum or no effect on connection demands that may appear at the same time. Ideally, during the optimization duration no other online request must be processed. This implies that any request that may appear during this time is placed on hold until the re-optimization process is concluded. More specifically, the waiting duration of an online request can be at maximum equal to the duration needed to calculate the re-optimized resource allocation. It is not necessary to wait for the overall duration that includes also the actual reallocation of the connection on the data plane, since the full information on the available resources is obtained at the end of the calculation phase.

The targeted duration of the re-optimized resource allocation computation phase is in the order of a few seconds (<2sec), while the whole process may practically take several seconds or even minutes depending on the data plane flexibility and automation in establishing optical paths.

It is highlighted that practically such a re-optimization process can be scheduled to run at a time of a day when minimum or even no connection requests are expected (e.g. very late at night).

Provisioning strategy

An interesting new feature that is considered, and strictly relates with the functions of the OPT-M, is the one that allows the provisioning of resources for a certain time and duration in the future, so that specific applications with strict service requirements to be accommodated. This feature refers practically to the capability of providing scheduling services for certain connection, as for example for a big social event that takes place in a stadium or when large quantities of data are to be transferred between datacentres.

The provisioning (or scheduling) strategy considers the re-allocation of resources over both layers of the network so that the required resources to support the scheduled event will be free at the time when needed, while other connections running at the same time will remain unaffected. It is noted that the strategy does not consider reserving the resources a priori. It simply guarantees the on time delivery of the required resources, while these may be used by other connections in the meantime.

5.1.2 Multi-layer re-optimization process

The multi-layer re-optimization process is called by the management plane through specific management applications that communicate directly with the OPT-M through the NBI. Optionally these applications can be scheduled to run periodically, e.g. at 4:00am every day, or triggered when certain network performance monitoring parameters are exceeding their threshold values. The latter requires that the monitored parameters are communicated to the management plane through the MLP-M or the NSDB. Also the NBI is informed to hold and stop sending service requirement requests to the MLP-M.

The process within the OPT-M is described with the following steps:

- First, the OPT-M collects the network status information from the NSDB and the relevant status information from the MLP-M, in case that a connection set-up is on progress.
- Next, the resource optimization algorithm is called and executed, with the goal to meet the defined optimization target (e.g. spectrum utilization, power consumption reduction, IP port count reduction etc.).
 - o The core of the algorithm could be the same like the one used in the MLP-M for the online processing case, thus it can be shared between the two modules. However, different optimization criteria require the use of different heuristics. This implies that a set of algorithms can be available and the one to use must be defined when the process is called.
 - o The default algorithm (if no specific choice is made) is the one that maximizes the number of connections that can be accommodated in the network. This is the algorithm that is implemented in the MLP-M and is based on the strategies defined in section 4.2.
- The obtained result with the reallocated connections is compared with the network status before the start of the process. The differences are identified and the connections that need to be reallocated are sent to the MLP-M, which orders them and then generates the requests for the SBI.
 - o For each of the reallocated connections, first a request for a new connection is sent. The old one is removed once the new one is installed.
 - o In case that a failure occurs during the re-optimization phase and the newly calculated connection cannot be reallocated then a message is returned to the MLP-M and the whole reallocation process is aborted. The OPT-M in this case can be called to run again considering the occurred failure.
- The online operation is restored.
 - o The reallocation process goes on in the data plane.
 - o The network status information is maintained in the MLP-M until the process is completed and the NSDB is updated. Also the released resources from the reallocated connections are made available to the new connection requests only after the NSDB is updated.

5.2 Recalculation of protection paths

Protection paths or routes are identified and reserved for applications that request this feature. This is done during the online resource allocation phase and executed by the MLP-M as shown in section 4.

One of the key options considered in ACINO is to allow the reserved protection paths to be utilized by best effort type of service requests, in order to maximize the overall resource utilization of the network. In case of a failure in the working path of the signals that are assigned the protection path, the best effort connections are dropped and the protection path accommodates the protected services.

Also another interesting case that is considered is to use the protection path for establishing service requests that require immediate connection, thus avoiding the long set-up time in particular through the optical layer and provided that no other resources are available for direct connection.

For both cases mentioned above and especially for supporting the latter case of immediate connection request, the identification of alternative protection paths is essential. This process can be handled by the OPT-M, by computing alternative protection paths in parallel to the online operation mode and suggesting these paths to the MLP-M. Additionally, the OPT-M may request the reallocation of certain connections or the establishment of alternative optical paths, in order to guaranty the existence of protection paths for the affected application. The whole process can be triggered dynamically by the MLP-M.

5.3 Operator-driven process to test network status under different scenarios

This process provides the capability to the network operator to run specific ‘what-if’ scenarios in order to examine how the network resources or the already established connections could be affected by certain actions. It can be used in order to provide network information to the operator, or to examine the network capability to accommodate large application demands in the future or even to plan for the required modifications and possible future expansions in the network infrastructure.

The specific process is triggered by a management application through the NBI and is purely executed within the OPT-M without interfering with the rest of the modules. Resource optimization algorithms with different optimization targets can be executed for a long period, (i.e. without any time constraints as in the re-optimization case discussed in 5.1), and with the goal to reach the global optimum.

For example, the module could check ‘what if a certain fibre link is removed’ (e.g. in order to save resources) and as a result how much extra bandwidth will be needed on the remaining fibre link. Another example could be ‘what if a certain high bandwidth connectivity with two or more types of application services will be requested’ (e.g. expecting to provide an offer to a large event organizer at a stadium) and how other connections are affected, or equally what changes are required so that all connections can be served.

6 Evaluation platforms, software tools and preliminary results

This section describes the adopted simulation platforms and provides some early results that demonstrate the main concept of the ACINO application aware optimization concept.

6.1 The Net2Plan platform

To implement the optimization strategies we choose the Net2Plan software tool [51], developed at the Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT), Cartagena, Murcia, Spain. We state here first our reasons for choosing the tool:

- One of the requirements of the ACINO project is the usage of free and open source tools. Net2Plan is free and open source. Thus, any optimization code written in the project that works with Net2Plan can be released together with Net2Plan.
- Net2plan has an effective graphical user interface (Figure 6.1), which lends itself to visualizing the network. Visualization of the network (or network model) is important in that it allows the network designer to easily identify the features and problems in the network design.
- Net2Plan has well-defined and documented data structures, such as node, link, demand, etc. This facilitates network modelling and optimization code writing. More importantly, it gives all partners in the project a common reference point, in that any module developed for Net2Plan will use the same data structures as the other modules.
- Multi-layer network modelling and optimization are supported. ACINO networks are strongly multi-layer-oriented, and Net2Plan satisfies this requirement.
- Some subroutines commonly used in network optimization are built-in. Examples are shortest path routines, topology connectivity test procedures and disjoint path routines. This shortens the time to develop new code modules.
- Similarly, the code for some example algorithms comes with the software package. The authors are experts in network optimization and want to demonstrate their algorithms. Even if these algorithms are not used in ACINO, the code included helps understand how to use Net2Plan.
- Service requirements can be entered as input to the optimization code. This is accomplished by so-called attributes, which consist of a key and a value, e.g. “latency – 20”. These attributes can then be read by the code. In addition, any other data that is not already supported in Net2Plan (bandwidth, fibre length, etc.) can be entered as attributes. This allows for flexibility in using the tool, as most any data can be entered and read.
- The authors have so far responded quickly and helpfully to queries and bug reports. User support gives extra value to the tool.

- Net2Plan supports user-defined reports. More precisely, this means code can be written that extracts useful statistics about the network, and presents them in a user-friendly way, i.e. as HTML pages.
- Net2Plan has potential to interact with a network orchestrator. This feature is important for ACINO Task 4.3. This way, ACINO does not have to develop separate code for network simulation and implementation, which will save time and manpower.

However, to make an evaluation of Net2Plan complete, we list here the disadvantages as well:

- Some small bugs are present in the code. While these have caused some setbacks, they have been minor and quickly overcome with the help of the Net2Plan authors.
- The graphical user interface has minor inefficiencies. For example, node names are in black, the same colour as the nodes, which makes them difficult to read for some network topologies. In addition, the data window cannot be stretched arbitrarily, which makes for slower use when a lot of data has to be examined.
- The tool for the ACINO simulation is developed by an entity that is not partner to the project. This implies limited influence on the future development of the tool. This is illustrated more with the next point.
- Net2Plan releases have introduced changes in the data structures, which required re-coding of our own code modules. In addition, some of the changes in the data structures are as of now inconsistent, in that a new data structure is not yet supported by the built-in functions. This has required writing translator code. Other than causing some time delays in the development, this has not yet impacted simulation runtimes significantly.

Figure 6.1: Net2Plan graphical user interface with reference network optical layer topology shown

6.2 Preliminary results with the Net2Plan platform

Two examples are presented in the next subsections that demonstrate the main ACINO concept in Net2Plan. It is noted that these examples does not implement fully the defined strategies but only part of them for specific network scenarios.

6.2.1 Simple six-node topology

In this paragraph we demonstrate the advantage of the ACINO concept over a network design that is application-agnostic. We use a simple network and traffic model on the Net2Plan tool. The test network topology is shown in Figure 6.2 (the screenshots in this Section are all taken using Net2Plan). This network can be thought of the IP network, however, the following description will show that it can also apply to other network layers.

Figure 6.2: A star-and-ring topology used as to get the first results

Note that the topology can be partitioned into a star and a ring of nodes and links, where six nodes are part of both the star and the ring. The star centre (named “Backbone Net or Central Hub”), to which all other nodes are directly connected can be thought of as either a single node, or a higher level network in a hierarchical topology. The six nodes in the network can then send some of their traffic to the hub, and the hub then forwards the traffic to the egress node.

Next, we describe the traffic model. The traffic is divided into two classes, where one class requires high bandwidth and low latency, and the other low bandwidth with no maximum latency specified. Specifically, one class requires a bandwidth of 1 unit and a latency of two hops and the other a bandwidth of 0.1 units. We thus provision the network so that all links to and from the hub (star links) have a capacity of four, and the remainder (ring links), have a capacity of 0.9. We assume no traffic splitting in the network. Consequently, the high-bandwidth/low latency traffic cannot be carried by the ring links.

When attempting to establish a connection for either service class, the connection will be blocked if the requested bandwidth is greater than the capacity of any path between the two endpoints, or if the latency of the shortest path is higher than the latency specified for the class.

Next, we describe two strategies for choosing a route through the network:

- Dumb: here we assume that the latency requirement for each service class must be respected, but we do not take special care to accommodate latency-sensitive traffic. We thus route all connections on shortest-hop paths.
- ACINO: The strategy here is that if the requested latency is not specified, a longer route can be chosen. This will leave the short paths available for latency-sensitive traffic. Algorithmically: Set all link weights to one. If the requested latency is low, then increase the link weights to six. Route on shortest paths.

An experiment with twenty runs showed that the ACINO strategy resulted in no blocking, while the Dumb strategy resulted in blocked traffic with every run. The blocked traffic demands are marked in Figure 6.3 taken from Net2Plan.

Figure 6.3: Net2Plan showing blocked traffic (red) and accommodated traffic (green)

6.2.2 Reference network topologies and traffic with latency awareness

Here we show a more complex example of testing and proving the ACINO approach to multi-layer optimization, and extract some interesting numerical results. We found that, with latency-aware traffic handling, the routing of IP packets and lightpaths affects the amount of the traffic that can be accommodated, and the time available to process the packets in each IP node.

Scenario setup

The IP topology is shown in Figure 6.4 as a Net2Plan capture. It consists of two parts, where, in each part, the nodes and the links form a ring and a star. The IP topology is thus very similar to the topology in Section 6.2. Note that in Figure 6.4 the two parts are disconnected. The real network has an IP link between every pair of routers in the same geographical region, but they are used only to carry traffic in the event of a failure.

Figure 6.4: Reference network core IP layer topology. The IP link between the routers in the same region is not shown

The optical fibre network, shown in Figure 6.5 as a Net2Plan capture, consists of 30 optical switches and 112 fibre-links. Here we limit our use of the network to one fibre per fibre-link, and assume that each fibre has 80 wavelengths. We also assume 40 Gb/s transceivers at all nodes. While more modern equipment is now available, 40 Gb/s everywhere simplifies our simulation and is sufficient to carry the simulated traffic. The lower rate also implies simpler modulation formats, thus allowing long lightpaths without having to resort to expensive regeneration.

We obtained kilometre distances for each fibre-link, and an end-to-end traffic matrix from the network provider. The difference between the largest and the smallest entry in the traffic matrix is two orders of magnitude, so the traffic distribution resembles an exponential one. We also observed that for each pair of the seven geographical regions, the traffic is split evenly between the two pairs core routers in the region. This is because in the real network, the access routers in each region are dual-homed on the core routers, and split their traffic between the core routers evenly.

Similar to Section 6.2, for each pair of nodes, we divide the end-to-end traffic in two application classes, where one class requires a low latency and the other one has no maximum latency requirement. In the real national network, IP layer functions such as classification are implemented in the metro and access parts of

the network. We can thus assume that the classification of the traffic is done in the access part of the network, and the core network only has to get the traffic across.

Figure 6.5: Reference network optical layer topology

The division to two classes is parametrized by parameter p , so that for each pair of nodes (A,B) whose total traffic is $T(A,B)$, the amount of low-latency traffic is $p \cdot T(A,B)$. In the simulation we set $p = 90\%$, 50% , 10% . Additionally, for each p , we will vary the required latency time.

Finally, although data exists for packet processing delays in networks (such as [53]), we instead want to measure the delay times in our model network. Note that, if the network has Optical Transport Network (OTN) switches co-located with the routers, the total delay imposed by the electronic processing comprises both IP packet processing and OTN switching. We assume the processing delay is the same for each packet in each router and OTN switch.

Network optimization

We assume the traffic matrix and parameter p are known to the network operator, but the sequence of connection demands is not. This lack of information, together with the given network topologies and parameters presents an optimization problem. Our strategy deals with both network layers so that it manipulates the IP, then the optical, then the IP again. As such it can be considered a joint multi-layer optimization approach ([1] pg. 2).

We will accommodate the traffic in two steps: IP-and-optical planning and IP routing. The planning step provisions the IP network resources as following. For each node other than the centre of the star (Madrid region), the IP link capacity on the link to Madrid is sized to carry all of the low-latency traffic sourced at the node. For the Madrid node, the IP link to each node A is sized to carry all of the low-latency traffic to A . For

each node in each ring, the outgoing IP links in the ring have enough capacity to carry the remainder of the traffic from the node.

We now describe the lightpath routing. First, the IP links are ordered, non-ascending, by the amount of traffic they must carry. We assume that multiple lightpaths can be used to implement the same link, which can be done by techniques such as IP link bundling. Then the lightpaths for each IP link are routed on the same sequence of fibre-links. We also assume no wavelength conversion in the network, which implies the same wavelength must be used on all fibre-links in each lightpath. The first-fit strategy is used to assign the wavelengths, and we try four shortest paths in non-descending order. In our simulation, no blocking was experienced due to a lack of wavelengths.

We use two types of routing for the lightpaths: *shortest propagation delay* and *balanced*. In shortest propagation delay, each fibre-link has a link weight equal to its light propagation delay, and we assume 200000 km/s propagation speed. However, this will result in some fibres having more than 90% utilization, while others, in the periphery of the network, will carry no lightpaths. Such concentrations of lightpaths are also problematic in case of fibre-cuts [54]. Instead, in balanced routing, the lightpaths will be on the shortest paths, where each fibre-link weight equals the number of wavelengths traversing the link. This results in more evenly distributed lightpath routes but longer lightpaths, which will impose additional latency.

The planning step dictates how traffic will be routed. We set the link weights so that the following shortest paths are computed. For each pair of nodes in the IP network, except for Madrid, traffic from low-latency demands is sent on the two-hop path to and then from Madrid. The rest of the traffic follows a path on the ring. If a path is congested, traffic is sent on any path that can carry the traffic, such that the low-latency traffic prefers the star links, and the rest the ring links. The planning and routing steps thus allow the low-latency traffic to experience a minimal delay in the core network. We refer to this routing as *latency-aware* IP routing. Otherwise, the IP routing is *latency-unaware* and packets follow any shortest-hop path.

Results

We randomly ordered the application demands and accommodated them one at a time, repeating the run for 100 orderings.

Table 6.1 shows, for $p = 90\%$, the maximum electronic processing delay, the amount of blocked traffic, on average, for each 100 runs, and the number of runs where at least some of the traffic was blocked. These results are shown for three application latency requirements (10, 20, and 40 milliseconds) and each lightpath routing type (balanced and short). We chose 10 ms because it is comparable with the propagation delays in the optical fibre network, and then relaxed it to two- and four-fold. Note that 10 ms turns out to be a threshold value as it causes blocking for one lightpath routing type, and no blocking if either the lightpath routing type or the latency requirement are changed.

Table 6.1: Latency-aware routing: maximum electronic processing delay, the amount of blocked traffic and the number of runs with blocking

10ms			20ms			40ms		
bal	short	none	bal	short	none	bal	short	none
-	2.1ms	5ms	4.1ms	7.1ms	10ms	14.1ms	17.1ms	20ms
1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

For the 10 ms requirement when lightpath routes are balanced, traffic is blocked even when no time is spent in electronic processing. Other results show that the longer lightpaths of balanced routing result in about 3 ms less allowed for IP router and OTN switch processing compared to shortest lightpath routing. When the propagation delay is ignored (denoted “none”) in Table 6.1, electronic processing can take at most half the allowed time, because latency-sensitive traffic is routed on two-hop paths in the IP network. As the service requirement latency increases, maximum electronic processing delay dominates over the propagation delay.

For comparison, Table 6.2 shows the results for latency-unaware routing. Note that the maximum processing times were set the same as in Table 6.1, to measure the amount of blocking when packets are routed oblivious to the latency requirement. Also, blocking occurs even for the relatively large latency requirement of 40 ms, and may be as high as 7%.

Table 6.2: Latency-unaware routing: maximum electronic processing delay, the amount of blocked traffic and the number of runs with blocking

10ms			20ms			40ms		
bal	short	none	bal	short	none	bal	short	none
1%	1%	1%	1%	7%	1%	1%	1%	1%
100	85	85	74	100	85	85	85	85

Next, in Tab. 3 we show the difference that changing p to 50% and 10% makes. Latency-aware routing can be observed to handle the change better than latency-unaware routing, as it causes considerably less blocking for both lightpath routing types. That more blocking is caused when $p = 10\%$ than when $p = 90\%$ can be explained by the fact that our IP link capacity sizing is biased to provisioning for latency-sensitive traffic first. On the other hand, our strategy allows for, when balanced lightpaths and latency-aware IP routing is used, an extra 700 μ s of maximum electronic processing time when p is reduced to 50% and the latency requirement relaxed beyond 10ms.

Table 6.3: Blocking and maximum electronic processing times to compare with the case of $p = 90\%$

p	Blocking		max electronic processing time compared to $p = 90\%$		
	Latency-aware	Latency-unaware			
50%	Same as for $p=90\%$	8%	10ms	20ms	40ms
				balanced, latency-aware	balanced, latency-aware
			+0ms	+0.7ms	+0.7ms
10%	4%	20%	0		

Summary of evaluation results

Using a multi-layer network optimization technique on the model of a real IP-over-WDM network, we have shown how intelligent handling of latency-sensitive traffic can be beneficial in terms of blocked application demands. In addition, for realistic application latency requirements and real fibre-link distances, we extracted the maximum time that packets can spend in routers and OTN switches. Such data may provide a guideline for planning the electronic layer hardware and packet processing software.

6.3 In-house planning tool with flex-grip optical layer emulation capabilities

In parallel with the development focusing on Net2Plan, we modified our in-house planning tool to support class awareness in order to be able to get some preliminary results and validate the concept quickly, while taking into account multilayer issues.

The original version of the in-house planning tool had support for

- Protection path routing, configurable per demand
- Link/node blacklist which can be used to avoid specific areas of the network
- Physical layer constraints, as a function of modulation format, so that increased spectral efficiency modulation formats can be used without sacrificing bit error rate performance.
- Source grooming, giving the possibility to route multiple requests using the same transceivers
- Reverse multiplexing, so that large requests can be split into smaller ones where needed

Even though this code was initially part of planning tool, sufficient state information is maintained so it can be used as part of a dynamic simulation tool, and small modifications were needed to add traffic class awareness.

6.3.1 Planning methodology

The multilayer planning problem we address is the following: given a network topology and source/destination traffic demands, appropriately dimension the link capacities and node ports to optimally

serve the given demand, while exploiting optical technologies (e.g. WSSs) also at the switching layer for transparent routing of lightpaths across transit optical nodes in an effort to minimize resource usage across the network. One way to achieve this is through traffic grooming. Traffic grooming aims to maximize switch port and link capacity utilization by appropriately routing traffic flows to pre-selected points in the network and aggregating them so that they can share common paths.

Figure 6.6: Generic multilayer node architecture

Figure 6.6 shows a generic multilayer node architecture. All fibres are connected to the WSS and the lightpaths are routed transparently. An optional aggregation layer (here represented by an OTN switch) is grooming traffic as specified by the grooming algorithm and the remaining traffic flows are handled by the IP router.

Our multilayer routing strategy is based on the heuristic multi-hop traffic grooming algorithm of [56]. The corresponding algorithm can be summarised in the following two steps:

- a. First, an attempt is made to set-up a transparent lightpath between every source-destination node pair using shortest path routing, subject to constraints in the number of transceivers at the two nodes, at the designated rates, and the availability of a wavelength in a given path connecting the two nodes, in order of decreasing request capacity. In this case, the two end-points are connected by means of a single transparent lightpath.
- b. If a direct lightpath cannot be established, an attempt is made to forward the traffic of the blocked requests using the spare capacity of the existing links; that is, the unused capacity of established connections (at L2/L3).

The initial assignment phase first routes all requests and stores the working and (optional) protection path for each. Subsequently, all unused fibre spans are removed from the network and not considered further. The wavelength assignment for each calculated path is done using a first fit algorithm over the available fibre spectrum. Then an optimization pass is used to improve the utilization of the transport network. The

optimisation pass tries to reroute requests in a random order to reduce the average nodal degree of the network. A multiple restart stochastic hill climbing optimisation algorithm [57] is used.

6.3.2 Concept validation using the in-house planning tool

To show that the in-house tool is suitable for initial evaluation of the concept (and later for integration as a subsystem within Net2Plan) we evaluated a scenario with two traffic classes: (a) high priority 1:1 protected traffic and (b) best effort traffic. To differentiate the multilayer handling of these traffic classes, we make the assumption that lightpaths are established only for the protected traffic requests and that best effort traffic only uses spare capacity of the already established protected traffic lightpaths. This in effect means that over the working path of each protected request/connection any spare capacity is available for use by best effort traffic, while over the protection path the full capacity of the lightpath is available.

To frame the handling of the two traffic classes in terms of the demand allocation options of section 0 (depicted in Figure 4.1) for the protected traffic option 3 “set up of a new IP link” is supported, while for best effort traffic options 1 “use of an existing (single-hop) IP link” and 2 “use on existing (multi-hop) IP route” are used, with a single-hop link preferred if available.

The scenarios are evaluated over the reference network optical layer topology shown in Figure 6.5, with 30 nodes and 56 bidirectional fibre links, assuming a WDM transmission system with 80 channels on a 50 GHz grid, utilizing 100 Gb/s transceivers with DP-DQPSK modulation.

We used a synthetic traffic matrix with a 1000 requests uniformly distributed over all 30 nodes. The data rate for each request was similarly uniformly distributed up to 100 Gb/s. The percentage of traffic in each traffic class was variable from 0 to 100%, with the first requests up to the given percentage assumed to be in the protected class.

The first test performed was to compare scenario (a) where each request is routed using a new lightpath (only option 3 of section 4.1) to scenario (b) where the traffic is routed taking into account its class. The results are shown in Figure 6.7.

In Figure 6.7 we see that the fibres required to accommodate the traffic for both scenarios depend on the percentage of protected traffic: more protected traffic requires extra lightpaths for the protection paths, and the limiting case where all traffic is protected the result is the same for both scenarios, while when all traffic is best effort, the class aware case is unable to serve any traffic since under the conditions of the test no lightpaths are established. In all other cases, the resources needed for the class aware scenario (b) are less than those required for the baseline scenario (a), while the probability of dropping best-effort traffic decreases with the establishment of more protected traffic paths.

Figure 6.7: Result of first class awareness test using in-house tool

The second test performed was to simulate a single fault and try to reroute the affected traffic. The fault simulated was a cut link. This affects the traffic in several ways: All traffic over the link is dropped and the protected traffic is routed over the protection paths, while all best effort traffic using these protection paths is similarly dropped. Then an effort is made to reroute the remaining best effort traffic over the network.

This was tested in a scenario with 30% protected traffic, where after routing 55 fibres were used to serve the 300 protected requests and a further 321 best effort requests were satisfied using the spare capacity available as described above. The protection event simulated was a single cut fibre, interrupting a total of 40 best effort connections. Out of these, 30 requests could be rerouted after moving the affected protected traffic over the allocation protection paths.

Those two tests were used to verify that the RMLSA engine is suitable as simulation infrastructure and that it can successfully support dynamic network state modification. Therefore integration with Net2Plan as a routing back-end is feasible.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ML	Multi-Layer
MLP-M	Multi-Layer Provisioning Module
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
NBI	North-bound Interface
OPT-M	Online Planning Tool Module
OTN	Optical Transport Network
SBI	South-bound Interface
SBVT	Sliceable Bandwidth Variable Transceivers
WSS	Wavelength-selective Switch

References

- [1] E. Palkopoulou, O. Gerstel, I. Stiakogiannakis, T. Telkamp, V. Lopez and I. Tomkos, "Impact of IP Layer Routing Policy on Multilayer Design [Invited]," *JOCN*, vol. 7, no. 3.
- [2] Ćiril Rožić, Dimitrios Klondis and Ioannis Tomkos, A Survey of Multi-layer Network Optimization (invited paper), ONDM, 2016.
- [3] E. Palkopoulou, O. Gerstel, I. Stiakogiannakis, T. Telkamp, V. Lopez and I. Tomkos, "Impact of IP Layer Routing Policy on Multilayer Design [Invited]," *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. A396 - A402, 2015.
- [4] E. Palkopoulou, O. Gerstel, I. Stiakogiannakis, T. Telkamp, V. Lopez and I. Tomkos, "Impact of IP Layer Routing Policy on Multi-Layer Design," in *Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, 2014.
- [5] T. Doiron, "SDN & Multi-layer Transport SDN: Notes from Layer123 SDN OpenFlow World Congress," [Online]. Available: <http://acgcc.com/sdn-multi-layer-transport-sdn-notes-from-layer123-sdn-openflow-world-congress/>. [Accessed 23 12 2015].
- [6] O. Gerstel, "Architectures for a Multi-Vendor IP-Optical Control Solution" (<http://sedonasys.com/images/Downloads/ONS16-Gerstel.pdf>), presented at Open Networking Summit, 2016.
- [7] O. Gerstel and V. Lopez, "The need for SDN in orchestration of IP over optical multi-vendor networks," in *European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC)*, 2015.
- [8] A. Mayoral, R. Vilalta, R. Casellas, R. Munoz and R. Martinez, "Traffic engineering enforcement in multi-domain SDN orchestration of multi-layer (packet/optical) networks," in *European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC)*, 2015.
- [9] S. Martinez, V. Lopez, M. Chamania, O. Gonzalez, A. Jukan and J. Fernandez-Palacios, "Assessing the Performance of Multi-Layer Path Computation Algorithms for different PCE Architectures," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference and Exposition and the National Fiber Optic Engineers Conference (OFC/NFOEC)*, 2013.
- [10] Ć. Rožić and G. Sasaki, "Cost of loop-free alternates in IP-over-WDM networks," *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 368 - 379, 2014.
- [11] Ć. Rožić and G. Sasaki, "Protection costs of a fully connected IP core network over a WDM ring", presented at *IEEE 4th International Symposium on Advanced Networks and Telecommunication Systems (ANTS)*, 2010.
- [12] C. Bowers, "Realizing the Benefits of Multi-Layer Packet-Optical Network Design," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference and Exposition and the National Fiber Optic Engineers Conference (OFC/NFOEC)*, 2013.

- [13] H. Zhu, H. Zang, K. Zhu and B. Mukherjee, "A Novel Generic Graph Model for Traffic Grooming in Heterogeneous WDM Mesh Networks," *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 285 - 299, 2003.
- [14] M. Chamania, M. Caria and A. Jukan, "Achieving IP Routing Stability with Optical Bypass," in *IEEE 3rd International Symposium on Advanced Networks and Telecommunication Systems (ANTS)*, 2009.
- [15] M. Chamania and A. Jukan, "A Comparative Analysis of the Effects of Dynamic Optical Circuit Provisioning on IP Routing," *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*, vol. 22, no. 2, 2013.
- [16] V. Gkamas, K. Christodoulopoulos and E. Varvarigos, "A Joint Multi-Layer Planning Algorithm for IP Over Flexible Optical Networks," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 13, no. 14, pp. 2965 - 2977, 2015.
- [17] L. Velasco, P. Wright, A. Lord and G. Junyent, "Saving CAPEX by Extending Flexgrid-based Core Optical Networks Toward the Edges [Invited]," *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 5, no. 10, pp. A171 - A183, 2013.
- [18] A. Klekamp, "Multi-Layer Network Optimization: Benefits of Elastic Optical Networks," in *14th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON)*, 2012.
- [19] I. Katib and D. Medhi, "IP/MPLS-over-OTN-over-DWDM Multilayer Networks: An Integrated Three-Layer Capacity Optimization Model, a Heuristic, and a Study," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 240 - 253, 2012.
- [20] D. Bhamare, A. Gumaste, P. Srivastava and M. Krishnamoorthy, "Multi-Layer Optimization for Service Provider Transport Networks," in *IEEE 38th Conference on Local Computer Networks (LCN)*, 2013.
- [21] N. Charbonneau and V. M. Vokkarane, "A Survey of Advance Reservation Routing and Wavelength Assignment in Wavelength-Routed WDM Networks," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 14, no. 4, 2012.
- [22] H. Ding, P. Yi and B. Ramamurthy, "Cost-Optimized Reservation and Routing for Scheduled Traffic in Optical Networks," *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 5, no. 11, pp. 1215 - 1226, 2013.
- [23] C. Vadrevu, M. Tornatore, R. Wang and B. Mukherjee, "Integrated Design for Backup Capacity Sharing Between IP and Wavelength Services in IP-Over-WDM Networks," *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 53 - 65, 2012.
- [24] O. Gerstel, C. Filsfil, T. Telkamp, M. Gunkel, M. Horneffer, V. Lopez and A. Mayoral, "Multi-Layer Capacity Planning for IP-Optical Networks," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 44 - 51, 2014.

- [25] M. Ruiz, O. Pedrola, L. Velasco, D. Careglio, J. Fernández-Palacios and G. Junyent, "Survivable IP/MPLS-Over-WSON Multilayer Network Optimization," *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 3, no. 8, pp. 629 - 640, 2011.
- [26] J.-L. Izquierdo-Zaragoza, J.-J. Pedreno-Manresa and P. Pavon-Marino, "Maximizing IP fast rerouting coverage in survivable IP-over-WDM networks," in *European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC)*, 2015.
- [27] W. Kmiecik and K. Walkowiak, "Survivable Overlay Multicasting in WDM Optical Networks with Dual Homing Architecture," in *International Conference on Optical Network Design and Modeling*, 2014.
- [28] K. Ashizawa, S. Okamoto, N. Yamanaka, E. Oki, A. Fumagalli and M. Veeraraghavan, "Application-Centric, Energy-Efficient Network Architecture ACTION, Based on Virtual Optical Slice Core and Deterministic Optical Access Network," *Journal of the Optical Society of Korea*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 340-345, 2015.
- [29] W. Hou, L. Guo and X. Wei, "Robust and Integrated Grooming for Power and Port-Cost-Efficient Design in IP Over WDM Networks," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 29, no. 20, pp. 3035 - 3047, 2011.
- [30] K. Christodoulopoulos and E. Varvarigos, "Evaluating flexibility degrees in optical networks," in *Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, 2015.
- [31] C. Abosi, R. Nejabati and D. Simeonidou, "Service Oriented Resource Orchestration in Future Optical Networks," in *Proceedings of 20th International Conference on Computer Communications and Networks (ICCCN)*, 2011.
- [32] O. Gerstel, V. Lopez and D. Siracusa, "Multi-layer orchestration for application-centric networking," in *International Conference on Photonics in Switching (PS)*, 2015.
- [33] R. Morais, J. Pedro and A. Nolasco Pinto, "Planning and Dimensioning of Multilayer Optical Transport Networks," in *17th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON)*, 2015.
- [34] Y. Zu, Y. Wang, L. Shao and W. Yang, "The Routing Algorithm of Multi-Layer Multi-Domain Intelligent Optical Networks Based on Ant Colony Optimization," in *15th IEEE International Conference on Communication Technology (ICCT)*, 2013.
- [35] S. Korotky, J. Simsarian and G. Atkinson, "Network Global Expectation Model of Optimized Routing and Grooming in Multi-Layer Service Transport," in *European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC)*, 2014.
- [36] D. van den Borne, "Carrier SDN: Centralised traffic engineering in multi-layer networks", in *Optical Connections Magazine*, no. 6, Q1 2016, pp. 34.
- [37] A. Autenrieth, "Multilayer Network Planning – A Practical Perspective", in *Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, 2016.

- [38] G. Beletsioti, G. Papadimtriou, N. Petros, “Energy-aware algorithms for IP Over Optical Networks”, *Journal of Lightwave Technology* (accepted for publication 2016).
- [39] G. Shen, R. S. Tucker, “Energy-Minimized Design for IP Over WDM Networks”, in *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 176–186, 2009.
- [40] S. Perrin, “Hardware Innovation and SDN Bring Renewed Promise to IP+Optical Integration Hardware Innovation and SDN Bring Renewed Promise to IP+Optical Integration”, *OFC Blog* (<http://www.ofcconference.org/en-us/home/about/ofc-blog/2016/march-1026/hardware-innovation-and-sdn-bring-renewed-promise/>), retrieved March 24th, 2016.
- [41] “The New Wave of IP + Optical Integration” (video), (<http://www.lightreading.com/carrier-sdn/sdn-technology/the-new-wave-of-ip--optical-integration/v/d-id/712203>), 2014.
- [42] M. Nikolayev, A. Morea, Y. Pointurier, J. C. Antona, “An efficient model for the multilayer network planning of IP-over-WDM networks”, in *European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC)*, 2015.
- [43] P. Papanikolaou, K. Christodoulopoulos, E. Varvarigos, “Multilayer flex-grid network planning”, in *International Conference on Optical Network Design and Modeling (ONDM)*, 2015.
- [44] P. Pavon-Marino, J. L. Izquierdo-Zaragoza, “Net2plan: an open source network planning tool for bridging the gap between academia and industry”, *IEEE Network*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 90 – 96, 2015.
- [45] J. L. Izquierdo-Zaragoza, J. J. Pedreno-Manresa, P. Pavon-Marino, “Net2Plan: An integrated open-source framework for multilayer network planning and in-operation simulation”, *17th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON)*, 2015.
- [46] Application-Centric IP/Optical Network Orchestration (ACINO), www.acino.eu
- [47] E. Palkopoulou, C. Meusburger, D. Schupke, L. Wosinska, T. Bauschert, “Combining multi-period and multi-layer network planning: Ignored potential?”, *36th European Conference and Exhibition on Optical Communication (ECOC)*, 2010.
- [48] H. Zhu, et al., “A novel generic graph model for traffic grooming in heterogeneous WDM mesh networks,” *IEEE/ACM Trans.* , 2003.
- [49] Martinez, S.; Lopez, V.; Chamania, M.; Gonzalez, O.; Jukan, A.; Fernandez-Palacios, J.P., "Assessing the performance of multi-layer path computation algorithms for different PCE architectures," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference and Exposition and the National Fiber Optic Engineers Conference (OFC/NFOEC)*, 2013 , vol., no., pp.1-3, 17-21 March 2013.
- [50] Mohit Chamania, Marcel Caria, Admela Jukan, Achieving IP routing stability with optical bypass, *Optical Switching and Networking*, Volume 7, Issue 4, December 2010, Pages 173-184.
- [51] Net2Plan, <http://www.net2plan.com>

- [52] Ćiril Rožić, Dimitrios Klonidis and Ioannis Tomkos, Latency-aware Multi-layer Network Optimization in IP-over-WDM Core Networks, European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC) 2016.
- [53] Optelion, A Sensible Low-Latency Strategy for Optical Transport Networks, white paper, 2014.
- [54] Ć. Rožić and G. Sasaki, "Cost of loop-free alternates in IP-over-WDM networks," JOCN, vol. 7, no. 4.
- [55] Open Network Operating System (ONOS), <http://onosproject.org/>
- [56] K. Zhu, Bi. Mukherjee, "Traffic Grooming in an Optical WDM Mesh Network", IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, vol. 20, no. 1, pp.122-133, 2002.
- [57] A. Juels, M. Wattenberg, "Stochastic Hill climbing as a Baseline Method for Evaluating Genetic Algorithms", University of California - Berkeley, CSD94-834 (1994)
- [58] O. Gerstel, M. Jino, A. Lord, S.J.B Yoo, "Elastic optical networking: a new dawn for the optical layer?" IEEE Communications Magazine, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. s12 - s20, Feb. 2012